

FORMATION OF PERIODIC PRECIPITATE IN THE ABSENCE OF A FOREIGN GEL. PART II. FERRIC HYDROXIDE SOL BY DIFFERENT METHODS.

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Ferric hydroxide sols have been prepared by acetate, carbonate and Krecke's methods for the study of periodic precipitation by the process of coagulation of these sols. The adsorption of sol by its own precipitate, the nature of the coagula which settle periodically and the speed of coagulation of the sols have been investigated. It has been shown that in obtaining the rings of precipitate by the coagulation of a sol, the adsorption of the sol by its own precipitate is not the only factor controlling the process,

In a preliminary study (Mittra, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1936, 6, 322) it was emphasised that for the production of periodic precipitate in sol by the process of coagulation, the adsorption of sol by its own precipitate, the nature of coagulum which settles periodically and also the speed of coagulation of the sol are the three important factors which determine the phenomenon. It is well known that the nature of the coagula, obtained by the addition of electrolytes to the sols of ferric hydroxide prepared by different methods, remarkably varies. Hence in order to study how far (i) the nature of coagulum, (ii) the speed of coagulation, and (iii) the adsorption of colloid by its own precipitate, control the process of the formation of rings, it has been necessary to have a systematic study of these and the results obtained on such investigations are detailed below.

With the object of comparing the sols of ferric hydroxide prepared by acetate, carbonate and Krecke's methods for the production of periodic precipitates, the sols of different degrees of purity were prepared. The original sols were diluted to the desired extents and these diluted sols were coagulated by mono- and bivalent electrolytes and the conditions of the coagula were noted after 24 hours. The volume of coagula, which determines the formation of rings, was found out by centrifuging for 5 minutes, 9 c.c. of the suspension obtained on thorough shaking of the coagula which settled periodically, out of the total volume of 20 c.c. of the sol-electrolyte mixture. It was observed that some of the precipitate which settled completely was peptised during the process of centrifuging. The amount of the precipitate thus peptised was estimated in each case. For finding the speed of coagulation, the sols were maintained at the concentration of 0.07378 g.

atom of Fe per litre. 10 C.c. of this sol were mixed with electrolytes, the total volume was made upto 20 c.c. and the time for complete coagulation noted. 8 C.c. of the sol-electrolyte mixture out of the total volume of 20 c.c. from such another set containing 0.000295 g. atom of Fe were taken in separate similar test tubes and set aside. The amounts of the uncoagulated sol from each of these 8 c.c. tubes were estimated successively at definite intervals of time by centrifuging the tubes for 5 minutes. The speed of the centrifuge was maintained at 2000 revolutions per minute. The coagulation-velocity curves have been drawn (not shown).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Ferric Hydroxide Sol (Acetate Method).

The sol was prepared (*cf.* Mitra and Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 315) and dialysed hot for 6 hours. It contained 0.25 g. atom of Fe per litre and its purity was 0.57.

TABLE I.

Sol conc. = 0.05 g. of Fe per litre. Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 20 c.c. of which 9 c.c. contain 0.000225 g. atom of Fe.

Amount of electrolyte.	Volume of coagulum.	Amount of precipitate peptised.
<i>2N-KCl.</i>		
6.5 c.c.	0.30 c.c.	0.0000112 g. atom.
6.0	0.35	0.0000134
5.5	0.40	0.0000223
5.0	0.40	0.0000223
<i>N/40-K₂SO₄.</i>		
2.5	0.25	0.0000223

With this concentration of the sol, only broken bands appeared with KCl; with K₂SO₄ as coagulant, an indistinct evidence for the bands was there. With higher concentration of the sol, the coagula were in gel state and no settling occurred after 24 hours.

TABLE II.

Speed of coagulation.

5 C.c. of 2 <i>N</i> -KCl (made upto 10 c.c.) coagulated 10 c.c. of the sol in 1 hour. (Ppt. conc.).		7 C.c. of 2 <i>N</i> -KCl (made upto 10 c.c.) coagulated 10 c.c. of the sol in 30 minutes.		4 C.c. of <i>N</i> / ₄₀ -K ₂ SO ₄ (made upto 10 c.c.) coagulated 10 c.c. of the sol almost instantaneously.	
Time.	Amount left in sol state out of 0·000295 g atom of Fe.	Time.	Amount left in sol state out of 0·000295 g. atom of Fe.	Time.	Amount left in sol state out of 0·000295 g. atom of Fe.
After 2 min.	No coagulation	After 2 min.	0·000256	After 2 min.	0·00002
15	0·000284 g. atom	15	0·000176	15	0·000014
45	0·00010	40	0·000048	40	0·000014
60	0·000048	60	0·000048		

The original sol was further purified by hot dialysis for 3 hours and contained 0·268 g. atom of Fe per litre, and its purity was 2·06.

TABLE III.

Sol concentration = 0·0268 g. atom of Fe per litre. Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 20 c.c. of which 9 c.c. contain 0·000126 g. atom of Fe.

Amount of electrolyte.	Volume of coagulum.	Amount of precipitate peptised.
<i>N</i> / ₂ -KCl.		
5·0 c.c.	0·5 c.c.	Nil
4·0	0·5	0·000029 g. atom
3·0	0·5	0·000031
2·5	Partial coagulation	
<i>N</i> / ₄₀ -K ₂ SO ₄ .		
2·5 c.c. to		
1·0 c.c.	0·5 c.c.	Nil
0·5	No] coagulation	

With this concentration and purity of the sol, numerous thick rings appeared (Plate I) on complete coagulation with lower concentrations of KCl. Higher concentration of KCl coagulated the sol more rapidly and only broken bands appeared there. There was a tendency for the formation of bands with K₂SO₄ as coagulant. Higher concentration of the sol yielded coagulum in gel state with no settling in 24 hours. With lower concentration of the sol rings appeared but all were broken due to complete settling of the coagula.

The speed of coagulation of this sol with KCl at its precipitating concentration is of the same nature as in Table II. The speed with K_2SO_4 could not be followed as the coagulation with this electrolyte was almost instantaneous.

The original sol was further purified by hot dialysis for 3 hours and contained 0.40 g. atom of Fe per litre, and its purity was 6.66.

TABLE IV.

Sol concentration = 0.04 g. atom of Fe per litre. Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 20 c.c.

Amount of $N/2$ -KCl.	Volume of coagulum.	
5 c.c.	0.7 c.c.	
4	0.7	
3	0.75	Nothing peptised
2	Partial coagulation	

With this concentration of the sol, the coagula were all in the gel state and did not settle at all when coagulated by KCl or K_2SO_4 .

TABLE V.

Sol concentration = 0.02 g. atom of Fe per litre. Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 20 c.c. of which 9 c.c. contain 0.0009 g. atom of Fe.

Amount of $N/2$ -KCl.	Volume of coagulum.	
5 c.c.	0.6 c.c.	Nothing peptised
4	0.6	Do
3	Partial coagulation	

With this concentration of the sol, the coagula were all in the gel state as before after 24 hours. After 48 hours, the coagula settled slightly and a few rings appeared. With still lower concentration of the sol, the coagula settled slightly but the amount of the coagula was so small that no bands developed fully.

Ferric Hydroxide Sol (Carbonate Method).

The sol was prepared by adding a solution of ammonium carbonate to ferric chloride solution in stages and with frequent stirring until the precipitate thus formed was peptised with difficulty. The resulting sol was purified by cold dialysis for 3 days and contained 0.142 g. atom of Fe per litre and of purity of 0.12.

TABLE VI.

Sol concentration = 0.0284 g. atom of Fe per litre. Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 20 c.c.

Amount of $N/40\text{-K}_2\text{SO}_4$.	Volume of coagulum.	Amount of precipitate peptised
5 to 3 c.c.	0.35 c.c.	Nil
2 c.c.	Partial coagulation	

With this concentration of the sol, there was a tendency for the formation of rings but as the coagulation with K_2SO_4 was almost instantaneous the bands could not develop. The sol could not be coagulated with KCl .

TABLE VII.

Speed of coagulation.

8 C.c. of $N/40\text{-K}_2\text{SO}_4$ (made upto 10 c.c.) coagulated 10 c.c. of the sol almost instantaneously.

Time.	Amount left in sol state out of 0.000295 g. atom of Fe.
After 2 min.	0.00048 g. atom
15	0.00032
30	0.00024

The original sol was further purified by cold dialysis for 4 days and contained 0.1396 g. atom of Fe per litre and its purity was 4.93.

TABLE VIII.

Sol concentration = 0.02792 g. atom of Fe per litre. Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 20 c.c.

Amount of $N/2\text{-KCl}$.	Volume of coagulum.	Amount of precipitate peptised.
2.5 c.c.	0.35 c.c.	Nil
2.0	0.40	Negligible
1.5	0.45	0.00018 g. atom
1.0	0.50	0.00054
0.5	Partial coagulation.	

With this concentration of the sol, quite prominent rings developed (Plate II) with lower amounts of KCl, *i.e.*, with 1.5 and 1.0 c.c.; with greater amounts of the electrolyte, broken rings appeared as the coagula settled more or less completely. K_2SO_4 coagulated the sol almost instantaneously producing no rings. Higher concentrations of the sol yielded coagula in gel state and no rings developed, and with lower concentration of the sol the coagula settled completely and the few rings which developed were all broken.

TABLE IX.

Speed of coagulation.

7 C.c. of $N/2$ -KCl made upto 10 c.c. coagulated 10 c.c. of the sol in 1 hour (precipitating concentration).

Time	Amount left in sol state out of 0.07295 g. atom of Fe.
After 2 min.	No coagulation
15	0.00283 g. atom
45	0.00116
60	0.00058

Adsorption of Sol.

The adsorption experiments were performed as stated in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*)

TABLE X.

Amount of precipitate taken each time = 0.35 g. of Fe. Amount of sol taken each time = 0.1262 g. of Fe.

Amount of $2N$ -KCl.	Amount of Fe left in sol state.	% Adsorption.
0 c. c.	0.134	-6.18
1	0.0186	84.90
2	0.000	100.00

In the absence of the precipitate, the same amount of the sol required 6.5 c. c. of the electrolyte for partial and 10.5 c.c. for complete coagulation.

The original sol was further purified by cold dialysis for 6 days. It contained 0.138 g. atom of Fe per litre and its purity was 8.62.

TABLE XI.

Sol concentration = 0.0276 g. atom of Fe per litre. Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 20 c.c. of which 9 c.c. contain 0.0001242 g. atom of Fe.

Amount of N/4-KCl.	Volume of coagulum.	Amount of precipitate peptised.
5 c. c.	0.40 c. c.	Nil
4	0.45	"
3	0.45	"
2	0.50	"
1	Partial coagulation	

With this concentration and purity of the sol, quite prominent rings appeared with lower concentration of KCl, but the number of rings was less than those obtained with the previous sol. K_2SO_4 coagulated the sol almost instantaneously, producing no rings.

TABLE XII.

Speed of coagulation.

1.5 C.c. of the sol made upto 10 c.c. coagulated 10 c.c. of the sol in 1 hour. (precipitating concentration).

Time.	Amount left in sol state out of 0.000295 g. atom of Fe.
After 2 min.	0.000270 g. atom
15	0.000185
45	0.000075
60	0.000044

TABLE XIII.

Adsorption of sol.

Amount of precipitate taken each time = 0.14 g. of Fe. Amount of the sol taken each time = 0.07 g. of Fe.

Amount of N/4-KCl.	Amount of Fe left in sol state.	% Adsorption.
0	0.078 g.	-11.4
1 c. c.	0.061	12.6
2	0.016	78.5
3	0.000	100.0

In the absence of the precipitate, the same amount of the sol required 8.0 c.c. of the electrolyte for partial and 10.2 c.c. for complete coagulation.

Ferric Hydroxide Sol (Krecker's Method).

The sol was prepared by adding a saturated solution of ferric chloride to boiling water drop by drop. The resulting sol was purified by hot dialysis for 50 hours. It contained 0.07378 g. atom of Fe per litre and its purity was 21.7.

TABLE XIV.

Sol concentration = 0.07378 g. atom of Fe per litre. Amount of sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 20 c.c. of which 9 c.c. contain 0.0003332 g. atom of Fe.

Amount of $N/2$ -KCl.	Volume of coagulum.	Amount of precipitate peptised.
6 c. c.	0.20 c. c.	0.000042 g. atom
5	0.15	0.000048
4	0.15	0.000078
3	Partial coagulation	

With this concentration of the sol, no rings appeared with KCl or K_2SO_4 . There was, however, a tendency for the formation of thin bands with KCl. The coagulum was of typically lyophobic nature.

TABLE XV.

Speed of coagulation.

4 C.c. of $N/20$ -KCl (made upto 10 c.c.) coagulated 10 c.c. of the sol almost instantaneously (ppt. conc.).

Time.	Amount left in sol state out of 0.000295 g. atom of Fe.
After 2 min.	0.000044 g. atom
15	0.000032
30	0.000029
60	0.000029

TABLE XVI.

Adsorption of sol.

Amount of precipitate taken each time = 0.14 g. of Fe. Amount of the sol taken each time = 0.02 g. of Fe.

Amount of N/2-KCl.	Amount of Fe. left in sol state.	% Adsorption.
0 c. c.	0.022	-6.8
1	0.003	85.4
2	0.000	100.0

In the absence of the precipitate, the same amount of the sol required 11.5 c.c. of the electrolyte for partial and 15.5 c.c. for complete coagulation.

The original sol was further purified by hot dialysis for 150 hours. It contained 0.082 g. atom of Fe per litre and its purity was 120.6. Though this sol was fairly pure, it behaved just as previously. The nature of the coagulum did not improve and no rings were obtained with it.

DISCUSSION.

From the foregoing results it may be seen that moderately pure sol of ferric hydroxide, prepared either by acetate or carbonate method, produces periodic precipitates, when coagulated by univalent electrolyte like KCl but the same sol prepared by Krecke's method does not produce such periodicities, irrespective of the nature purity and concentration of the sol taken. It is well known that the properties of the same sol, like that of ferric hydroxide, prepared by different methods vary widely according to the method of preparation adopted. The colloidal micelle from a sol prepared by acetate and carbonate methods are moderately hydrated. This can be judged from the data on the volumes of the coagula yielded by different sols on coagulation which are remarkably more hydrated in the case of the sols prepared by acetate and carbonate methods. It has been generally noted that an optimum volume of the coagula, which settle periodically, obtained from 9 c.c. out of the total volume of 20 c.c. of the sol-electrolyte mixture, has been 0.5 c.c. Values above and below this optimum volume are not favourable for the process of ring formation. It has also been found that there are two conditions for greater or less values of the volumes of coagula obtained from a definite amount of Fe_2O_3 in colloidal condition. The one is that if the coagulation of the sol be effected rapidly for a certain purity of it, the volume of coagulum becomes less. For with rapid coagulation, the colloidal particles are discharged completely and the precipitate is of a compact mass. On the other hand, if the sol be made purer by dialysis, the speed of

coagulation becomes rapid but as the colloid becomes more hydrated the coagulum occupies greater volume.

From the data on the speed of coagulation it is seen that the coagulation of sol with K_2SO_4 is practically complete within two minutes after the addition of the electrolyte (*cf.* Tables II, VII). The coagulation being rapid, this electrolyte is not suitable for producing rings. With KCl the coagulation is slow near about its precipitating concentration and sufficient coagulation takes place fifteen minutes after the addition of the electrolyte (*cf.* Tables II and IV). This electrolyte is suitable for producing rings, provided the optimum volume of the coagulum be 0.5 c.c. under the conditions as stated above. With increasing amounts of KCl, the speed of coagulation increases (*cf.* Tables II, XII) and both the qualities and the number of rings fall. In the case of the ferric hydroxide sol prepared by Krecke's method, the speed of coagulation with KCl is rapid and is of the same nature as in Tables II and VII and this sol does produce periodicities as in other cases. During the process of centrifuging, specially in the cases of slow coagulation, it was observed that some of the precipitate got peptised and the amount of the precipitate thus peptised increases with the lesser amounts of the electrolyte; because in the latter case the speed being slow, the coagulum already appeared coexists with its own sol and adsorbs the uncoagulated sol. This loosely adsorbed sol comes out as the coagulum becomes more and more compact during centrifuging. This adsorption of sol can explain the S-shaped nature of some of the coagulation velocity data (Tables II and IX). The coagulation proceeds at first slowly, then rises quickly as the coagulum appears more and more and finally falls off again. In these cases quite good rings appear. With the increasing amounts of the coagulating electrolyte, the amount of the peptised sol during centrifuging decreases and no good rings appear here due to small adsorption of sol by the coagulum.

Thus the adsorption of sol by its own precipitate is an important factor in the formation of rings. But it has been observed that the adsorption is greatest in the case of the ferric hydroxide sol prepared by Krecke's method where no good rings are obtained. In the sols prepared by acetate and carbonate methods the adsorption is also appreciable. It may be concluded, therefore, that the adsorption of sol by its own precipitate is fairly general in colloids and is not a guiding factor in the process of the formation of rings in sols by coagulation, as are the other two factors *viz.* (i) the nature of the coagulum and (ii) the speed of the coagulation.